

Factors Affecting the Motivational Factors of the 21st Century Educators

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ABSTRACT

The quality of teaching and learning is determined not just by the quality of teachers, but also the quality of the environment where they are working. This study aims to track the motivational factors of basic education educator. The results show that teachers are well motivated when they have an environment that support their way of life as a teacher. It also shows that teachers are well satisfied on their job security. On the one hand, their eagerness to improve and develop supports the previous studies that indicates the importance of intrinsic supports for their development.

KEYWORDS: 21st Century Educators, Motivation, Descriptive methods of Research

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INTRODUCTION

Teacher motivation plays a significant role in promoting excellence in teaching and learning. Motivated educators are generally more likely to motivate learners to learn in the classroom to guarantee that instructional reforms and happiness and fulfillment emotions are implemented. While teacher motivation is essential to the process of teaching and learning, it is not extremely driven by several educators. This observation should be taken seriously and it was, therefore, necessary to investigate the factors influencing teacher motivation to achieve the educational goals in each learning institution (Nyakundi, 2012).

Moreover, teachers motivation will have a pivotal characteristic in schooling. Hettiarachchi (2013) indicated that if educators are upset with their job, this can additionally cause inclined schooling outcomes for college kids in public faculties. Therefore, making plans their career in increase also can limit strain. Increasing educators revel in, their capacity to have relationships with people and their psychological capability is high-quality for growing their motivation. moreover, instructors are simply as in particular encouraged to reveal their very personal intellectual development as they're for their college students' development (Menyhárt, 2008).

Although the prevailing look at became inspired by using the hassle of trainer attrition, this text does not observe

instructor attrition without delay. as an alternative, we examine assumed antecedents of trainer attrition, specifically trainer process delight and motivation to go away the coaching profession. One purpose of the observe turned into to study relations among school context variables and trainer job satisfaction, as well as the motivation amongst Norwegian teachers to depart the coaching career. information the members of the family among faculty context variables and trainer process pride is important due to the fact the college context or operating situations can be changed and stepped forward. some other motive become to investigate whether the members of the family between faculty context variables on the only hand, and teacher activity pride and motivation to depart the teaching profession on the opposite, had been, at least in part mediated through teachers' feeling of belonging and bodily and emotional exhaustion (Skaalvik, 2010).

According to Ifinedo (2003) employee motivation is a complicated and tough time period to define; therefore a specific definition of this concept is elusive as the perception accommodates the characteristics of character and scenario as well as the belief of that state of affairs with the aid of the man or woman. Lewis, Goodman and Fandt (1995) assert that company's liveliness comes from the incentive of its employees, despite the fact that their abilities play just as critical a role in determining their paintings overall

performance as their motivation. encouraged and committed personnel may be a determining issue in the success in an institution.

Furthermore, there are numerous outside factors that affect instructors' motivation and demotivation, the studies literature on instructor demotivation regularly discusses the most important elements which include the issue associated with curriculum and teaching as a profession. The former has been discussed in the present literature on instructor motivation a few results frequently underlined the necessity for the curriculum's flexibility and for no longer overloading it with numerous goals to satisfy due to the fact they could be not possible to attain (e.g. Johnson, 2000). A curriculum must be flexible and drawn in keeping with the teaching situations and college students' competence to save you demotivation of teachers and damage the teaching manner; in addition, path books also are being evolved in keeping with the flexible and handy curriculum in accordance with the scholars' potential and needs in coaching (Johnson, 2000). The latter, this is the teaching as a profession, refers to the popularity of the price of teaching.

Background of the Study

This study is anchored on the theory of Maslow. The theory developed a principle approximately the rank and pride of various human wishes and how people pursue their wishes. Within the agency, very last repayment and health care are some of the advantages which assist a worker to meet their physiological needs. Safety needs can be manifested while personnel feels secure in their operating surroundings. When that is glad, the employee's can focus on feeling as although they belong to the place of business.this could be in a shape of having proper courting with the colleagues and supervisors. Once satisfied, the employee will searching for to feel as even though they're valued and preferred by using their colleagues and their organisation. The very last step is wherein the employee seeks to self-actualize; where they need to grow and increase a good way to emerge as the whole lot they're capable of becoming.

Objective of the Study

This study aims to measure the motivational level of the teachers within the school premises. This includes job security, working conditions, and personal and professional development. It also sought to analyze the reasons behind each of the level of the indicator. Because the researcher believed that a motivated teacher is very essential in producing a conducive learning environment and quality learners. Hence, this study was conducted.

Methodology

This study utilizes a descriptive research method to measure the motivational level of the teachers. The combination of its characteristic summary and correlational statistics, along with its focus on specific types of research questions, methods and outcomes is what distinguishes descriptive research from other research types.

Results and Discussions

A motivated educator is essential to a successful classroom. They will look at coaching via a one of a kind lens, and, in doing so, motivate their students of their getting to know too. Motivation enables to energize, direct and sustain nice behavior over a protracted time period. It includes operating

closer to goals and tailoring activities to reaching this motive. It also enables to pressure creativity and curiosity, sparking the choice wanted for college students to need to research more.

Job Security

Job security is the assurance that you'll keep your job without the risk of becoming unemployed. Your job could be secured through terms of an employment contract, collective bargaining agreement or labor legislation that prevents arbitrary termination (Dayton, 2019).

Table1.

In table 1, the data show the motivational level of teachers on job security. The data implies that fairness in dealing with employees/teachers was the highest weighted mean of 4.6 which verbally described as very high. This entails that teachers were treated fairly in the school and that's why they are motivated. On the one hand, grievance committee got a lowest weighted mean of 3.6 which verbally described as high. Further, The indicator job is stable and trouble free was rank as the 2nd highest weighted mean. It implies that the grievance committee does not function that well to address the problems and grievances of teachers thus giving slow solutions to the problems. But over-all, teachers are very much motivated with mean of 4.31 under security aspect.

Working Conditions

The quality of teaching and learning is determined not just by the quality of teachers, but also by the environment in which teachers work. Together with the intrinsic benefits of teaching, working conditions, which are shaped by factors such as salary range, compensation, bonuses and rewards; working time, staff-student ratios, good school leadership, infrastructure and facilities, influence teachers' satisfaction with the workplace, their tasks and the nature of the job as well as teachers' ability to do their work well and engage with students OECD (2019).

According to the National Center for Education Statistics to deliver high quality education, schools must attract, develop, and retain effective teachers. Working conditions play an important role in a school's ability to do so. Schools that are able to offer their teachers a safe, pleasant, and supportive working environment and adequate compensation are better able to attract and retain good teachers and motivate them to do their best. Teachers' working conditions are important to students as well as teachers because they affect how much individual attention teachers can give to students. Large class sizes or disruptive students, for example, can make both teaching and learning difficult. Some aspects of

teachers' working conditions go along with the job regardless of where a teacher works. For example, teacher salaries tend to be low relative to those earned by similarly qualified individuals in other professions regardless of the type or location of the school. Other aspects of teachers' working conditions, such as school safety, vary widely from school to school. Thus, in addition to being concerned about teachers' working conditions in general, we need to pay attention to the types of schools that tend to have desirable or difficult working conditions and, for equity reasons, to the characteristics of the students who attend them.

Table2.

Table 2 shows that motivational level of the teachers in terms of working conditions. respondents have a completely excessive degree of motivation with a median of four.7 in these statements “working hours are excellent” and there is interdependence between superiors and instructors”. each the superiors and instructors are interdependent with each other specially in accomplishing a challenge. running hours are good wherein instructors spend more time in doing other things like checking after coaching. It means that the operating surroundings is right and no longer disturbing thus enable teachers to be motivated. Lowest imply is underneath this statement “equipments are adequate” with a mean of 3.8 which corresponds to a high stage of motivation. It means that there are inadequate gadget which might be available for the students to use. the inducement of instructors lowers down because they from time to time had a tough time in locating available substances to beautify learning. standard suggest four.29 which corresponds to a totally excessive stage as a consequence teachers are encouraged in the factors under operating situations.

Personal and Professional Development

Education is a lifetime commitment. It doesn't prevent after earning a diploma and starting a profession. Through continuing schooling, career-minded people can continuously enhance their competencies and turn out to be more gifted at their jobs. Personal and professional growth is a need to an educator in any area of their profession. One have to not stop getting to know beneath this degree, it talks approximately how administrators give the proper reimbursement particularly to people with grasp's degree. Additionally, it includes if there are opportunities given like sending them to seminars and education a good way to beautify their abilities.

Table3.

Table 3 shows the personal and professional growth of teachers and how they are being acknowledged by their administrators. These include given the chance to pursue their graduate studies or given the chance to participate in any seminars that will enable them to grow. As shown in the table above, the highest mean is 5.0 under this statement “awarding of teachers every year” which corresponds to a very high level of motivation. It implies that a simple recognition and appreciation to all the sacrifices and efforts of the teachers were being acknowledged thus they perform well. Lowest mean is 4.1 which correspond to a high level of motivation under this statement “teachers were sent to seminars and trainings for advancement”. It implies that teachers were not given that full attention especially for their growth and development. Some of the teachers were sent to seminars and trainings especially outside school seminars and trainings. Teachers lack some training and seminars that they can use especially in having the appropriate teaching strategies.

Conclusions

Based on the finding of the study, Teachers have a very high motivational level in the following aspects: Job security, Working conditions and personal and professional development. It shows that teachers are highly motivated to perform well in their tasks being given. Further, Reinforcement is also true about motivation. The more an educator is reinforced, the more he will become motivated thus yield to productivity. The more an educator is satisfied with his work, the more it will increase productivity or better output. This implies that teacher's productiveness will also depend on their level of motivational factors. Susan (2019) stated that there should be a proposed training's and seminars for the teachers relating to digital citizenship and how to be a responsible digital citizen. According to Mahler (2018) Knowledge and motivation of a teacher are two unchallenged, essential characteristics for successful education. Whilst the relevance of teachers' professional knowledge for successful students' learning has been studied in a sophisticated manner for years, the meaning of teachers' motivational orientations for students' performance still lacks a differentiated consideration. Futher, the results on his study noted that a positive trend in the relationship between enthusiasm for teaching the subject and students' performance. The results provide a differentiated picture about the importance of motivational orientations for the characterization of an effective teacher. We discuss our findings in terms of possible effect mechanisms and their relevance for further research on teacher motivation and the improvement of teacher education programmes.

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